

Highlights

Key Metrics to Improve the Efficiency of Scrum Teams: Analytic Network Process Approach

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- Agile software projects fail due to inefficient teams.
- We used semantic networks and analytic network process to identify key metrics.
- Key metrics are Velocity, Cycle time, Work capacity, and Focus factor.
- Organizations can prioritize improvements based on the key metrics.

Key Metrics to Improve the Efficiency of Scrum Teams: Analytic Network Process Approach

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Abstract

Agile software development and the Scrum method are currently the most successful ways to develop software projects and represent a viable alternative to traditional project management. However, many software projects that use Scrum still fail due to inefficient teams. This study addresses a research gap where no comprehensive research based on semantic networks and the analytic network process had been proposed to systematically assess the key metrics that affect Scrum team efficiency. Using semantic network construction, literature review, and the analytic network process, we identified and prioritized key metrics through weighted analysis to determine which factors most significantly impact Scrum team efficiency. The five most important metrics that affect Scrum team efficiency are Velocity, Cycle time, Work capacity, Focus factor, and Targeted value increase, followed by additional metrics ranked by their calculated weights. The results of this study offer Scrum teams valuable practical insights into the metrics that affect team daily operations. Organizations can now prioritize their improvement efforts strategically and direct resources toward the most impactful factors. By focusing on these identified key metrics, Scrum teams can systematically assess their performance and enhance their effectiveness in dynamic software development environments.

Keywords: agile software development, analytic network process, Scrum, Scrum metrics, semantic networks, team efficiency

1. Introduction

Scrum and agile methodologies are extensively adopted in software organizations and demonstrate clear advantages over traditional approaches. However, many organizations face challenges in realizing consistent team performance through Scrum adoption. Despite widespread use, agile teams often underperform due to team inefficiency. Research indicates that awareness of team efficiency and key efficiency metrics supports better estimations and outcomes, yet a systematic approach to identify and prioritize the metrics that distinguish efficient from inefficient Scrum teams does not exist.

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While individual metrics and success factors have been studied, no systematic research has applied semantic networks and analytic network process to identify and prioritize key Scrum team efficiency metrics. A literature search yielded fewer than five papers directly addressing this intersection. Organizations therefore lack a comprehensive list of key metrics prioritized by importance, making it difficult to focus improvement efforts strategically. To establish the extent of this gap, we conducted a systematic literature search and review in Web of Science and Scopus scientific databases. Our search terms included “mcda” (for multiple-criteria decision analysis), “mcdm” (for multiple-criteria decision-making), or “anp” (for analytic network process) in combination with “scrum” or “agile”, and “metric*”. We directly included the analytic network process in the search as the most appropriate operations research method for our research. The search results yielded fewer than ten possibly related papers in English from any year. Notably, none of the papers found were related to agile project management, Scrum, or metrics. This confirms that no comprehensive research based on multi-criteria decision analysis and operations research has been proposed to assess the metrics that affect Scrum team efficiency. To address this research gap, we formulate two research questions:

- RQ1: What affects the Scrum team efficiency?
- RQ2: How can we evaluate the efficiency of Scrum teams?

This study applies semantic networks and analytic network process to systematically identify and prioritize the key metrics that affect Scrum team efficiency. By identifying and ranking these metrics according to their calculated weights, organizations can now prioritize their improvement efforts strategically, directing resources toward the most impactful factors. As members of an interdisciplinary research team that connects systems theory and operations research with project management research and the influence of human factors on teamwork, this research establishes a comprehensive, decision-based operations research approach to determine the key metrics that affect Scrum team efficiency and distinguish efficient teams from inefficient ones.

2. Related Work

2.1. Agile Project Management

Project management is the application of specific processes and principles to initiate, plan, execute and manage the way that new projects and changes are implemented within an organization. Project management includes planning, delegating, monitoring, and controlling of every aspect of the project, and motivating participants to achieve the project objectives [5]. Project is a temporary endeavor undertaken to create a unique product, service, or result. Project teams achieve the outcomes using a variety of techniques, such as traditional and agile approaches to project management. Traditional project management uses waterfall-based methods to manage projects while agile project management utilizes agile methods [37]. The waterfall model originated in the 1950s and was later documented by Royce [39]. Waterfall-based methods rely heavily on project outcome controls instead of fast feedback [31].

Agile project management and software development are different approaches to develop software projects [12], that emerged as a response to the software development

crisis in the 1990s and represents an alternative to traditional ways of managing software projects [47]. Unlike traditional approaches that focus on planning ahead, agile methods aim at incremental delivery of business value in each iteration, close collaboration with the customer, and fast feedback loop. The Manifesto for Agile Software Development [6] declares four fundamental values and twelve principles of agile software development. Agile methods perform well on highly innovative and start-up software projects, as described by Highsmith [22] and Niewöhner et al. [36]. Agile methods promise to achieve high productivity and provide high quality software, and awareness of the level of team productivity helps achieve better estimations and results [32]. According to the 17th State of Agile Report by Digital.ai [14] and Kadenic et al. [26], the most utilized agile frameworks or methods are Scrum or hybrid methods based on Scrum.

2.2. Scrum Method

Scrum is an agile framework that encourages team collaboration and helps people, teams, and organizations generate value through adaptive solutions for complex problems. Scrum is primarily used for developing software projects. Scrum is founded on lean thinking and empiricism that leads to higher work efficiency and effectiveness. Scrum defines three pillars of empiricism and five core values. The three pillars of empirical Scrum are transparency, inspection, and adaptation. The five core values are courage, focus, commitment, respect, and openness. The core values give directions to Scrum teams regarding their work, actions, behavior, and enable successful use of Scrum [46]. Scrum team is the fundamental unit of Scrum. The Scrum team includes one Product Owner, one Scrum Master, and multiple Developers. Scrum is based on teams, as opposed to individual actors. Teams get things done [54]. Teams are at the heart of Scrum as the most important factors that contribute to the performance and success of a project and its success [62].

All work in Scrum is done in fixed-time iterations, called Sprints. A Sprint typically lasts two weeks. During each Sprint, the Developers undertake the work required for achieving the Sprint Goal and a usable product Increment that contributes towards the Product Goal. Scrum events are meetings used for planning, organizing, and revising the work. Each Scrum event is a formal opportunity to inspect and adapt Scrum artifacts [46]. Scrum events include Planning, Daily Scrum, Review/Demo, and Retrospective. See figure 1 for the details of the Scrum process. The Sprint begins with Planning, continues with Daily Scrum meetings held by a Scrum team on a daily basis, and closes with Review/Demo and Retrospective at the end of a Sprint. Product Backlog Refinement is performed during the entire Sprint.

Scrum utilizes artifacts for managing work in the Sprint. Product and Sprint Backlogs are used for planning and organizing User Stories that represent features requested by the customer. The separation of both Backlogs enables funneling Backlog items into Sprints [33]. An Increment represents a concrete step toward the Product Goal. The Scrum team delivers a new Increment after completing each Sprint. Planning Poker is the most frequently applied technique to estimate the work effort of the User Stories selected for the Sprint [57]. Scrum teams use the Definition of Done to specify output criteria for completed work and visual tools to track the progress of work. In Scrum, team performance is measured using team velocity [60]. Burn-down Chart visualizes the team's velocity, measured in story points.

Figure 1: Sprint overview (source: own, adapted from scrum.org)

2.3. Scrum Adoption and Implementation Challenges

Scrum is considered a highly flexible and productive method for managing and improving projects in software companies [19], that potentially leads to increased team productivity [34]. The Scrum method is convenient for delivering innovations, prototyping, and introducing new solutions [54]. Scrum is based on lean thinking and is strongly influenced by Lean production and Toyota Production System [29]. Scrum is extensively used nowadays in software engineering and software projects [24] as well as in a wide range of other applications outside the traditional project management [25]. Many organizations adopt agile practices to meet ad-hoc business requirements and improve team collaboration and customer experience. As stated by the latest CHAOS Report [11] on current trends in agile software development, agile projects are three times more likely to succeed than waterfall projects. Regardless of extensive use of agile methodologies, many software projects still fail. The report indicates that 19% of software projects fail and 50% of software projects are challenged. López-Martínez et al. [30] mention that while Scrum process is easily understood, introduction and adoption of Scrum in companies is difficult due to incompatible culture in the companies. The success of agile adoption and self-organizing agile teams depends on the support of senior management [23]. In a survey by van Kelle et al. [58], the authors found that successful adoption of agile development practices is a key success factor for a Scrum project. According to Verwijs [61], Scrum is the world's number one approach to agile software development. However, over 70% of Scrum adoptions fail.

2.4. Team efficiency

In earlier times, efficiency referred to quantified technical assessment in engineering that emerges from measurements of performance in machines and thermodynamics of energy [2]. In the field of quality management, efficiency refers to doing things right, i.e., whatever is performed is done in the most suitable way with respect to the available resources [53]. Efficiency indicates achieving maximum productivity by optimally utilizing input resources to produce a specific outcome with a minimum amount of waste and unnecessary resources [48]. In agile software development, the most valuable resource is the work effort of team members. Team efficiency focuses on adhering to project quality standards within defined budgets and times, while team effectiveness indicates how well the team meets product quality requirements [13]. Matthies and Dobrigkeit [33] work

with a similar definition, where efficient team performance is assessed in terms of adherence to schedules and budgets. Verbruggen et al. [60] introduce the idea of process efficiency, which is seen as a driver for delivering value. The authors describe being efficient as having a low amount of waste in the production process. The concept of waste is closely related to the core concepts of Toyota Production System, described by Liker and Ross [29]. Efficiency can be calculated as the ratio between output and input. See equation 1. In Scrum, output refers to the value delivered by an agile team, while input refers to the cost of work effort required to deliver that value.

$$efficiency = \frac{output}{input} \quad (1)$$

Many organizations aspire to improve efficiency and standards of software development by implementing agile practices such as Scrum [16]. The results of research by Kadenic et al.[26] indicate that being successful at Scrum depends on team maturity, team composition, and the importance of all three Scrum roles. Furthermore, effective teamwork is crucial in agile software development[52]. In a comparable manner, Torrecilla and Salinas [56] present metrics such as *Team velocity*, *Percentage of accepted work*, or *Target value increase* to help track and improve team efficiency. Wagner and Ruhe [64] discovered that soft factors concerning productivity are not analyzed with equal detail as more technical factors. Research by Almeida and Carneiro [3] suggests that metrics are key elements that can provide valuable information about effectiveness and efficiency of software development process in a Scrum ecosystem. Drury-Grogan and Meghann [15] work with iteration objectives, which represent objectives developed and designed by the team for each Sprint. The iteration objectives are reviewed by the team at the end of the Sprint. According to the authors, little research has been conducted that relates iteration objectives to project management success factors.

2.5. Semantic Networks

A semantic network is a graphic notation for representing knowledge in patterns of interconnected nodes (vertices) and edges (arcs), forming a connected graph. In a semantic network, nodes describe individual objects in the analyzed domain, and edges describe relations between interconnected nodes. Semantic networks provide a convenient tool for organizing large quantity of related information. Early versions of semantic networks were used in linguistics, philosophy, and psychology, while later computer implementations were developed for artificial intelligence and machine learning [49]. Semantic networks often follow a scale-free pattern of connectivity, as most nodes have relatively few edges that are joined together by a small number of hubs with many connections [51].

Semantic networks can be used for representing human knowledge in computers and enabling automated processing of this information. Semantic means “relating to meaning in language or logic, while a semantic network forms a graphical representation of structured knowledge. Such networks are composed of nodes and links. Nodes represent concepts, such as words or phrases, and links represent semantic relations between the connected nodes. The links are tuples (*source, semantic relation, target*) that encode knowledge [8]. Semantic networks explicitly denote a taxonomic hierarchy that provides organized information for better conceptual organization and reduced space complexity. Inheritance links such as *is-a*, *is-a-kind-of*, and *is-a-part-of* form the backbone of this

hierarchy [7]. A class is conceptually an abstract entity, and an object is a physical entity [65]. We used semantic networks to represent the main concepts and ideas of Scrum.

2.6. Analytic Network Process

The analytic network process (ANP) is a method used in multi-criteria decision analysis. ANP is a generalized form of the analytic hierarchy process (AHP). The main difference between the two approaches is that AHP models a decision problem as a structured hierarchy with a goal, decision criteria and sub-criteria, and alternatives [40], while ANP utilizes a network with a goal, control criteria organized in clusters, and alternatives for modeling the problem [41], [43]. ANP can model complex decision problems, where a hierarchical model is not sufficient to resolve the problem because many decision problems cannot be structured hierarchically [42]. Both methods use pairwise comparisons to evaluate the weights of the components in the hierarchy (for AHP) or network (for ANP) and rank the alternatives in the decision. The pairwise comparisons relate to the links and semantic relations in semantic networks. Moreover, both decision-making methods incorporate the human factor since the choices between alternatives are made by the decision maker. Decision-making involves criteria and alternatives to choose from, and the criteria usually have varied importance and the alternatives in turn vary in our preference for them on each criterion [41], [42].

ANP decomposes a decision problem into a network of partial problems that are easier to analyze and evaluate. Unlike AHP, ANP allows for feedback connection and loops [41]. Criteria and sub-criteria in ANP are considered equal, as they are represented by nodes in a network. Each node in an ANP network can be compared to any other node provided that both nodes are linked together. Nodes can also be grouped into clusters and assigned cluster priorities. An ANP network is represented by a super matrix which includes all nodes in the network, both horizontally and vertically. The result of the comparisons in the network is an unweighted super matrix. This is then normalized and synthesized into a weighted limit matrix [42], [43]. ANP has been applied to a wide range of decision-making problems in multiple fields, such as project management, risk assessment, supplier selection, and product design [55]. ANP is widely used for decision processes in the fields of economics, management, and finance, especially in sustainable projects that facilitate the participation of many stakeholders, as explained by Gonzalez-Urango et al. [17].

3. Data and Methods

3.1. Construction of Scrum Concept Map and Semantic Network

We created a concept map to visualize the main concepts of Scrum. To assemble the Scrum concept map, we analyzed in detail two seminal works on Scrum: Scrum by Sutherland [54] and The Scrum Guide by Schwaber and Sutherland [46]. From these key concepts, we constructed the Scrum semantic network and modeled them as domains and groups (nodes) in the network. We added relations between concepts and ideas based on these publications and our empirical experience from collaboration in Scrum teams. The Scrum semantic network utilizes all types of semantic network relations, namely *is-a*, *is-a-kind-of*, *is-a-part-of*, and custom relations. We used the Scrum semantic network as

the organizing framework for categorizing the metrics identified in the literature review and synthesis.

3.2. Literature Search and Review Design

We conducted a systematic literature review on Scrum team efficiency. For the literature review, we adopted a systematic search and review process, as proposed by Kitchenham et al. [27] and described by Grant and Booth [18] in their typology of reviews. The review process consists of three phases: Planning, Conduction, and Report (Figure 2). The Planning phase focuses on defining research objectives and research questions, selecting appropriate scientific databases to conduct the search, selecting relevant keywords, defining inclusion and exclusion criteria, and defining quality criteria. The Conduction phase involves searching for papers using the selected scientific databases and keywords, applying the search criteria defined in the Planning phase, and analyzing the retrieved papers. The Report phase covers synthesizing the retrieved information and interpreting the results.

Figure 2: Literature search and review process (source: adapted from Kitchenham et al. [27])

In the Planning phase, we defined our search criteria based on the research questions, formulated in the Introduction. We selected Scopus and Web of Science scientific databases as the main data sources for our search. Selecting high-quality scientific databases ensures the relevance and quality of retrieved papers. In keyword selection, we organized our search terms into four thematic groups connected to our research. First, we included the *scrum* and *agile* keywords. *Scrum* directly represents the Scrum method, while including *agile* was necessary to filter out information about Scrum that is not connected to agile software development, such as scrum in rugby and sports. Second, we included the *team** keyword (which extends to *team*, *teams*, and *teamwork*) because we are interested in teamwork and team efficiency. Third, we used the keywords *effic** and *effect** to cover efficiency and effectiveness. Finally, we included the *metric** keyword because we sought papers exploring metrics as quantitative factors to measure efficiency. To maximize recall for our primary search terms, we searched titles, abstracts, and keywords. For *metric**, however, we extended the search to full indexed content.

We defined inclusion and exclusion criteria to be applied in two stages: within the search queries and during the subsequent full-text content analysis. Inclusion criteria were English-language, peer-reviewed publications from 2015–2024 with available full-text. We accessed full-text content of the papers through institutional access, open access, or other available sources. Exclusion criteria included duplicate papers, extended versions of conference papers, short papers, reviews, and non-accessible papers. For duplicate papers, we preserved the most recent version. For extended conference papers,

we retained related journal papers and removed the conference versions on the same topics. We omitted short papers, extended abstracts, keynote talks, and editorials. We excluded non-accessible papers because we could not analyze their full-text contents. Eligible papers had to address Scrum, agile software development, and Scrum team efficiency. We focused specifically on collocated or hybrid small Scrum teams in commercial environments. Hence, we excluded large-scale Scrum frameworks (LeSS, SAFe, Scrum of Scrums), distributed and virtual Scrum teams, and studies examining Scrum in educational or research contexts. We also excluded papers focusing solely on productivity, as we were specifically interested in efficiency metrics. We applied these scope-based criteria during the full-text analysis of selected papers.

In the Conduction phase, we applied the search criteria defined in the Planning phase to refine and construct the final search queries. We executed searches across the selected databases in February 2025 and iteratively reviewed the retrieved results. Using reference manager tools and manual review, we evaluated each result against our inclusion and exclusion criteria, identified and removed duplicates, checked full-text availability, and manually reviewed abstracts and full-text content to assess relevance to our research. We retained only papers relevant to our research with available full-text content. Finally, we applied the scope-based criteria defined in the Planning phase, removing papers that described large-scale Scrum-based methods (such as LeSS or SAFe) or educational and academic use of Scrum. In the Report phase, we analyzed the full-text content of the selected papers to extract relevant information and classify and consolidate the metrics.

3.3. Metrics Synthesis, Classification, and Consolidation

We synthesized and interpreted the metrics from the reviewed papers related to Scrum team efficiency. We used the Scrum semantic network as the organizing framework for categorizing these metrics. We required that the identified metrics be measurable and quantifiable, as described in quantitative project management by Shouche et al. [45]. For example, *Team size* counts as a metric, while *Coordination issue* does not. We included metrics such as *Team satisfaction*, based on empirical experience from teams that quantified these metrics using numerical scales. We divided the metrics into domains and groups according to the Scrum semantic network, their description and use. However, we omitted the Scrum Theory domain because it does not relate to any specific metrics. We followed the categorization and description of metrics provided in the reviewed literature. During metrics synthesis, we revised and updated the Scrum semantic network and its relations. We combined similar metrics whose meanings were identical or sufficiently similar. We generalized or renamed several metrics. For example, *Weighted methods per class* became the more general *Weighted units of code*, which accommodates a wider range of programming paradigms. We also adapted time-unit estimates to accommodate both Story Points and fixed time units. We retained most metrics in their original form, but renamed or merged some metrics to maintain consistent granularity and better reflect their purpose. Figure 3 illustrates the three steps of this process: synthesis and framework definition, classification and organization, and consolidation and refinement. We also removed metrics that are not specific to the Scrum domains, specifically *Time to market*, *Customer satisfaction score*, *Net promoter score*, and *Return on investment*. These metrics are more product-related and applicable across any project management methodology, not solely Scrum or agile frameworks.

During the metric synthesis process, we applied consolidations and refinements across domains. In the Sprint domain, we included *Team size*, renamed *Iterations* to *Expected number of iterations*, merged *Done User Stories* and *Done* into *Number of accepted User Stories*, consolidated *Estimation variance* and *Completed versus committed User Stories* into *Estimation accuracy*, merged User Story statuses into *Number of User Stories by status*, and combined *Team velocity* and *Actual velocity* into *Velocity*, while *Cycle time* includes *Lead time*. In the artifacts domain, *Number of User Stories in the Sprint* includes *Amount of stories*, while *Sprint Burn-down* and *Epic Burn-down* reflect the ratio of remaining and completed work at the Sprint and Epic levels respectively. In the Tech domain, *Source lines of code* covers *LOC*, *SLOC*, and *KLOC*, *Code complexity* includes *Cyclomatic complexity*, and *Weighted units of code* replaces *Methods per class* as a more general term. We also consolidated defect-related metrics: *Defects count* covers *Story defects* and *Defects debt*, *Defects density* includes *Weighted defects*, and *Defect removal percentage* encompasses *Defect spill* and *Containment effectiveness*. Figure 3 illustrates the three steps of this process: synthesis and framework definition, classification and organization, and consolidation and refinement.

Figure 3: Metrics synthesis, classification, and consolidation workflow (source: own)

3.4. Expert Metrics Evaluation and Scoring

We applied the synthesized metrics framework to quantify the occurrence and depth of each metric in the 13 selected papers. We assigned a score ranging from 0 to 3 to each occurrence of a metric in the relevant papers for Scrum team efficiency: 0 if the metric is not present, 1 if the metric is only mentioned in the text, 2 if the metric is briefly described in the text, and 3 if the metric is described in detail or reflects a key concept in the paper. Two agile experts with 10+ years of experience in Scrum independently scored each metric occurrence using the defined criteria. After independent scoring, we compared assessments for each paper-metric pair. When both experts assigned the same score, that score was finalized. When scores differed, both experts reviewed the relevant papers together, discussed the evidence for each score level, and assigned a final consensual score. We then calculated the total efficiency score for each metric and subsequently aggregated scores for groups and domains. Figure 4 illustrates the three steps of this process: framework definition, expert evaluation and consensus, and score aggregation. See supplementary materials [28] (scrum-efficiency-metrics-scoring.xlsx) for the aggregated scores of metrics, groups, and domains.

Figure 4: Metrics evaluation and scoring workflow (source: own)

3.5. ANP Network Design and Weighting

We used ANP to determine the weights of metrics identified in the literature review and synthesis. We designed an ANP network based on the Scrum semantic network described in the previous text. The network consists of domain clusters and metric group clusters, with uni-directional relations between domain and group clusters, and uni-, bi-, and self-directional relations among domain clusters. Each domain cluster contains metric group clusters, which in turn contain individual metric nodes (Figure 5). To ensure analytical relevance, we removed domains and groups that do not contain any metrics with assigned scores, as they do not contribute to the subsequent analysis.

Figure 5: ANP Network design with domains, groups, and metrics (source: own)

We calculated metric weights using the assembled ANP network with a modified approach: instead of the standard pairwise comparisons, we derived weights directly from the metric scores assigned during metric synthesis. We omitted metrics without assigned scores because they contribute no weight to the subsequent analysis. We employed a bottom-up approach across three levels. First, within each metric group, we calculated individual metric weights by comparing metric scores to determine their relative importance. Second, we aggregated these weights at the group level by summing metric scores within each group and adjusted individual metric weights accordingly. Third, we constructed an incidence matrix from the domain relations and calculated domain weights, then re-normalized all metric weights accordingly. We utilized Python, AhpAnpLib library [1], and Excel to calculate the metric weights. See Supplementary Material [28] (scrum-efficiency-metrics-calculations.xlsx) for the calculations of metric weights.

4. Results

4.1. Scrum Concept Map and Semantic Network

We constructed a two-level Scrum concept map organized into eight main concepts, as displayed in Figure 6. The first level contains the fundamental concepts of Scrum, while the second level contains details for each concept. The concept map is structured around the central concept of Scrum method with eight main concepts: Pillars (Transparency,

Inspection, Adaptation), Values (Commitment, Focus, Openness, Respect, Courage), Roles (Product Owner, Scrum Master, Developer), Events (Planning, Review/Demo, Retrospective, Daily Scrum), Iterations (Sprint, Release), Metrics (Velocity, Burn-down), Visualization (Scrum Board, Burn-down Chart), and Artifacts (Product Backlog, Sprint Backlog, Increment).

Figure 6: Scrum concept map (source: own)

We constructed the Scrum semantic network from the concepts and hierarchy identified in the Scrum concept map, as illustrated in Figure 7. We identified five core domains related to Scrum: Sprint and Events (also referred to as Sprint), Artifacts and Visualization (also referred to as Artifacts), Scrum Theory, Team, and Tech. Each domain contains corresponding groups of concepts and activities represented as nodes, with relations represented as edges. We rendered concepts derived from the Scrum concept map in gray and those added later during the efficiency metrics synthesis in white. Following the semantic network relation types described in the Methods section, the network includes three types of relations: relations between domains, relations between groups, and relations between a group and a domain. Each relation between domains represents multiple underlying relations between these domains or their constituent groups in a given direction, including self-relations.

The Sprint domain includes the Sprint and Scrum events: Sprint Planning, Review/Demo, Retrospective, Daily Scrum, and Release. The Artifacts domain contains Scrum artifacts such as Product Backlog, Sprint Backlog, and Increment, and visualization tools: Scrum Board and Burn-down Chart. The Scrum Theory domain covers

Figure 7: Scrum semantic network (source: own)

the three pillars: Transparency, Inspection, and Adaptation, and the five core values: Commitment, Focus, Openness, Respect, and Courage. The Team domain includes Performance and Motivation groups, the Team, and the three Scrum roles: Product Owner, Scrum Master, and Developers. The Tech domain covers software development: Implementation, Quality, and Testing. For example, the Scrum team participates in all events and utilizes artifacts such as the Sprint Backlog and Scrum Board, or the lack of quality of implementation and tests increases technical debt. We revised the Scrum semantic network after conducting a literature search and review. In the revision, we added Performance and Motivation groups in the Team area and Quality group in the Tech area. The Scrum semantic network serves as a framework for classifying efficiency metrics, which we iteratively refined through literature search and review.

4.2. Identified Papers on Scrum Team Efficiency

The search queries returned 92 initial results. After reviewing for duplicates and similarities, we retained 77 papers. Following full-text availability checks, 60 accessible papers remained. Manual review of abstracts and full-text content identified 25 papers related to our research. Application of the scope-based inclusion and exclusion criteria resulted in the removal of 12 additional papers. The final selection yielded 13 papers relevant to our research (Figure 8). The resulting papers are listed in Table 1. The table contains the identifier, authors, reference, and paper title according to the reference.

Figure 8: Literature search and review results (source: own)

ID	Authors	Reference	Title
A23	Almeida and Carneiro	[4]	Perceived Importance of Metrics for Agile Scrum Environments
B22	Butt et al.	[9]	A Software-Based Cost Estimation Technique in Scrum Using a Developer’s Expertise
C24	Chakravarty and Singh	[10]	A Dissection of Agile Software Development in Changing Scenario and the Sustainable Path Ahead
G16	Gupta et al.	[20]	Challenges in Adapting Agile Testing in a Legacy Product
H16	Harvie and Agah	[21]	Targeted Scrum: Applying Mission Command to Agile Software Development
M21	Matthies and Dobrigkeit	[33]	Experience vs Data: A Case for More Data-Informed Retrospective Activities
N24	Natarajan and Pichai	[35]	Behaviour-Driven Development and Metrics Framework for Enhanced Agile Practices in Scrum Teams
S18	Sandu and Salceanu	[44]	New Approach to Agile Cycles Containment Effectiveness Metrics in Automotive Software Development
T15	Torrecilla-Salinas et al.	[56]	Estimating, Planning and Managing Agile Web Development Projects Under a Value-Based Perspective
V16	Vlietland et al.	[63]	Aligning Codependent Scrum Teams to Enable Fast Business Value Delivery: A Governance Framework and Set of Intervention Actions
V19	Verbruggen et al.	[60]	Process Efficiency – Adapting Flow to the Agile Improvement Effort
V22	Vazifeh-Noshafagh et al.	[59]	Maturing the Scrum Framework for Software Projects Portfolio Management: A Case Study-Oriented Methodology
Z21	Zheng et al.	[66]	Key Performance Indicators for the Integration of the Service-Oriented Architecture and Scrum Process Model for IoT

Table 1: Papers related to Scrum team efficiency (source: own)

4.3. Efficiency Metric Scores

The systematic evaluation of Scrum efficiency metrics across the 13 papers produced results organized in five tables: Table 2 (Sprint domain), Table 3 (Artifacts domain), Table 4 (Team domain), Table 5 (Tech domain). Each table presents metric names, groups, references (identifiers) with partial scores, and total scores. Within each domain, metrics are further organized into functional groups from the Scrum semantic network. The References column identifies which papers contain each metric, while the Total score column displays the total efficiency scores for each metric. These identified metrics associated with Scrum team efficiency answer the first research question, RQ1: “What affects the Scrum team efficiency?”

Metric	Group	References	Total score
Sprint length	Planning	A23 (2)	2
Team size	Planning	A23 (2), B22 (2)	4
Team members’ engagement score	Planning	A23 (2)	2
Expected number of iterations	Planning	T15 (2)	2
Estimated project duration	Planning	T15 (2)	2
Number of tasks	Daily Scrum	A23 (2)	2
Number of tasks in progress	Daily Scrum	A23 (2)	2
Number of impediments	Daily Scrum	A23 (2)	2
Estimated time for a task	Daily Scrum	A23 (2)	2
Remaining time for a task	Daily Scrum	A23 (2)	2
Workload distribution per team member	Daily Scrum	A23 (2)	2
Number of completed tasks that day	Daily Scrum	A23 (2)	2
Number of accepted User Stories	Review/Demo	A23 (2), V22 (2)	4
Number of rejected User Stories	Review/Demo	A23 (2), V22 (2)	4
Estimation accuracy	Review/Demo	A23 (2), C24 (1), Z21 (2)	5
Percentage of accepted User Stories	Review/Demo	T15 (2)	2
Number of User Stories by status	Review/Demo	V22 (2)	2
Number of User Stories completed in a Sprint	Retrospective	A23 (2)	2
Number of tasks completed in a Sprint	Retrospective	A23 (2)	2
Number of User Stories in initial release plan	Release	V22 (2)	2
Number of User Stories in actual release plan	Release	V22 (2)	2
Number of User Stories in final release plan	Release	V22 (2)	2

Table 2: Metrics in the Sprint domain (source: own)

Metric	Group	References	Total score
Number of added User Stories	Product Backlog	A23 (2)	2
Number of deleted User Stories	Product Backlog	A23 (2)	2
Number of User Stories in Backlog	Product Backlog	A23 (2)	2
Business value	Product Backlog	A23 (2)	2
Number of User Stories in the Sprint	Sprint Backlog	A23 (2), V16 (1)	3
Number of tasks in the Sprint	Sprint Backlog	A23 (2)	2
Time spent to implement a task	Sprint Backlog	A23 (2)	2
Sprint Burn-down	Sprint Backlog	A23 (2), C24 (1), M21 (1), N24 (1)	5
Time the User Story is open	Sprint Backlog	V16 (2)	2

Table 3: Metrics in the Artifacts domain (source: own)

Metric	Group	References	Total score
Targeted value increase	Performance	A23 (2), T15 (2)	4
Team member turnover	Performance	A23 (2)	2
Velocity	Performance	A23 (2), B22 (3), C24 (1), N24 (1), T15 (2), Z21 (2)	11
Work capacity	Performance	A23 (2), T15 (2), V22 (2)	6
Cycle time	Performance	C24 (1), M21 (1), V16 (3), V19 (3)	8
Interruption time	Performance	V19 (2)	2
Team efficiency	Performance	V19 (2)	2
Focus factor	Motivation	A23 (2), T15 (2)	4
Team satisfaction score	Motivation	A23 (2)	2
Number of unsatisfactory User Stories	Motivation	M21 (1)	1
Say:do ratio	Motivation	N24 (1)	1

Table 4: Metrics in the Team domain (source: own)

Metric	Group	References	Total score
Source lines of code	Implementation	B22 (3), H16 (1)	4
Code complexity	Implementation	H16 (1)	1
Nested blocks depth	Implementation	H16 (1)	1
Weighted units of code	Implementation	H16 (1)	1
Application performance	Implementation	C24 (1)	1
Acceptance tests per User Story	Testing	A23 (2)	2
Functional tests per User Story	Testing	A23 (2)	2
Test automation percentage	Testing	A23 (2), N24 (2)	4
Unit tests per User Story	Testing	A23 (2)	2
Test coverage	Testing	G16 (1)	1
Test feedback time	Testing	M21 (2)	2
Defects count	Quality	C24 (1), N24 (3), S18 (1)	5
Defects count per User Story	Quality	A23 (2), N24 (3)	5
Defects density	Quality	A23 (2)	2
Customer defects density	Quality	S18 (2)	2
Defect detection percentage	Quality	G16 (1)	1
Defect removal percentage	Quality	C24 (1), S18 (3)	4
Average time to fix defects	Quality	C24 (1)	1
Defects severity	Quality	C24 (1), N24 (3)	4

Table 5: Metrics in the Tech domain (source: own)

4.4. ANP Network for Scrum Metrics

We constructed an ANP network based on the Scrum semantic network and the identified metrics. Figure 9 displays a diagram of the network structure showing four domain clusters: Sprint, Artifacts, Team, and Tech, along with twelve group clusters. Each domain cluster contains metric group clusters, which in turn contain individual metric nodes. The figures display the first two levels, with domain clusters rendered in gray and group clusters rendered in white.

Figure 9: ANP network with domain and group clusters (source: own)

The figures display the first two levels, with domain clusters rendered in gray and group clusters rendered in white. For example, the Artifacts domain cluster contains Product Backlog and Sprint Backlog group clusters, while the Product Backlog cluster includes the metrics: *Number of added User Stories*, *Number of deleted User Stories*, *Business value*, and *Number of User Stories in Backlog*. The network incorporates bidirectional relations between nodes within clusters, unidirectional relations between nodes in different Artifacts domain group clusters, and self-directed relations for each node.

Figure 10 shows the details of the Artifacts domain subnetwork. In this diagram, we simplified the connections between clusters for clarity. Each relation between clusters represents multiple relations between nodes in those clusters. For example, each node in the Artifacts cluster is connected to each node in the Product Backlog cluster. Clusters and nodes in the remaining three domains are designed equivalently to the Artifacts domain.

4.5. Key Metrics to Improve Scrum Team Efficiency

We employed ANP network methodology to calculate the key metrics that affect Scrum team efficiency. Table 6 displays these key metrics, including metric names, domains, group classifications, and weights. The metrics are sorted by weight in descending order and reported to four decimal places.

Figure 10: Clusters and nodes in the Artifacts domain (source: own)

Metric	Domain	Group	Weight
Velocity	Team	Performance	0.0971
Cycle time	Team	Performance	0.0706
Work capacity	Team	Performance	0.0530
Focus factor	Team	Motivation	0.0353
Targeted value increase	Team	Performance	0.0353
Estimation accuracy	Sprint	Review/Demo	0.0259
Sprint Burn-down	Artifacts	Sprint Backlog	0.0259
Defect count	Tech	Quality	0.0259
Defect count per User Story	Tech	Quality	0.0259

Table 6: Primary key metrics that affect Scrum team efficiency (source: own)

The key metrics are: *Velocity*, *Cycle time*, *Work capacity*, *Focus factor*, and *Targeted value increase* (weights > 0.030), followed by *Estimation accuracy*, *Sprint Burn-down*, *Defect count*, and *Defect count per User Story* (weights > 0.025). A comprehensive list of all 61 metrics with their corresponding weights is provided in Table A.7 in the Appendix A. The ranked metrics and their calculated weights answer the second research question, RQ2: “How can we evaluate the efficiency of Scrum teams?”

5. Discussion

In our research, we investigated the factors that affect Scrum team efficiency. We examined why software projects fail despite agile approaches being more successful than traditional methods. Research and practice suggest that the causes of failure can be related to team immaturity, lack of discipline in the team, inadequate use of Scrum, and technical difficulties such as low code quality. We proposed two research questions to address this issue and identified metrics that affect Scrum teams.

5.1. Interpreting Efficiency Metrics

Metric weights represent relative importance of the metrics in determining Scrum team efficiency. The most important metric is *Velocity*, with a weight of 0.0971. In our

paper, *Velocity* covers related metrics such as *Team velocity* and *Actual velocity*. *Velocity* measures the amount of work a team can accomplish during a Sprint. A stable velocity enables reliable Sprint planning and indicates mature, synchronized team execution. The second most important metric is *Cycle time*, with a weight of 0.0706. *Cycle time* represents the total time the team spends on a given task from start to end. *Cycle time* reflects the team’s ability to deliver value quickly and reduce work-in-progress accumulation, directly impacting customer satisfaction and market responsiveness. The third most important metric is *Work capacity*, with a weight of 0.0530. *Work capacity* defines realistic team capacity after accounting for meetings and interruptions, enabling honest work estimation and commitment. The fourth and fifth metrics are *Focus factor* and *Targeted value increase*, with weights of 0.0353, measuring team concentration on committed work and progression toward business outcomes.

The results show that *Velocity* is approximately 37.5% more important than *Cycle time*, which is 33.2% more important than *Work capacity*, while *Work capacity* is 50.1% more important than the subsequent metrics. This hierarchy underscores the primacy of delivery speed and team productivity. Most metrics in the top 15 efficiency metrics belong to the Team and Tech domains, with *Sprint Burn-down* as the only Artifact domain metric. Four of the top five metrics belong to the Team domain and Performance group, indicating that team-level factors are foundational to Scrum efficiency.

5.2. Literature Alignment and Practical Implications

We expected that the key metrics would include *Velocity* and *Sprint Burn-down*, as these metrics are routinely mentioned in professional literature in agile project management such as Scrum by Sutherland [54] or The art of agile development by Shore [47]. Our findings largely confirm these expectations. In addition, we can relate the most important metrics in the results to contemporary scholarly literature. As pointed out by Verbruggen et al. [60], *Velocity* is the most important metric to measure agile team performance. The importance of *Velocity* is further stressed by Torrecilla and Salinas [56] and Butt et al. [50] as a key factor that contributes to team productivity. Team-based metrics in the Team domain and Performance group are the most crucial factors that contribute to the success of a software project, according to Verwijs and Russo [62]. The importance of teamwork and team design choices that relate to metrics such as *Work capacity* and *Focus factor* from the Team domain is suggested by both de Melo et al. [34] and Strode [52]. These findings suggest that organizations should prioritize team performance metrics such as *Velocity* and *Cycle time* as foundational elements in their improvement initiatives, establishing team efficiency first before implementing the technical metrics traditionally emphasized in software engineering.

5.3. Unexpected Findings and Research Gaps

In agreement with the results of our research, Kadenic et al. [26] state that the success of Scrum adoption depends on team composition and maturity. According to Mashmool et al. [32], precise estimations as well as high quality software help achieve high efficiency. Accurate estimates relate to the *Estimation accuracy metric*, while high software quality is reflected by the metrics in the Tech domain and Quality group such as *Defects count*. *Cycle time* and *Targeted value increase* metrics correspond with the core of Scrum, which aims at delivery of business value in each iteration [6]. A short cycle time reflects fast and

efficient delivery of business value to the customer, thus reducing waste and unnecessary resources [48]. The higher the increase in value delivered, the more efficient the team.

However, our findings reveal notable divergences from expectations. We did not expect *Source lines of code* to rank high because in software engineering, this metric is considered obsolete. More significantly, technical metrics in the Tech domain such as *Defects density*, *Application performance*, and *Test coverage* ranked surprisingly low in our results. This discrepancy warrants attention: common industry experience and technical debt literature suggest that technical difficulties and code quality are common causes of software project failures. These results imply that in agile contexts, team-level factors rather than technical metrics are the primary determinants of Scrum efficiency, reframing how we conceptualize software project success. We view this gap between empirical results and practical experience as a key research opportunity to explore in future work, particularly through direct field studies with practicing Scrum teams.

5.4. Scope and Methodological Limitations

Research limitations include those related to the literature search and review, research process, and synthesis of metrics. In the literature search and review, we aimed at a representative, not exhaustive, list of publications, and selected Web of Science and Scopus scientific databases as the main resources. We excluded publications that included no quantitative metrics related to Scrum team efficiency in the iterative process of literature review, metrics analysis and synthesis. We may revisit the omitted papers in future research. In metrics synthesis, we intentionally omitted metrics that are not associated with any domain in the Scrum semantic network. These metrics include general product metrics, such as *Cost variance* or *Net promoter score*, which are not primarily associated with Scrum or agile software development. We also intentionally omitted the Scrum theory domain from the ANP network and calculations because it represents abstract conceptual knowledge rather than measurable activities.

We used an expert-based scoring method to rate the occurrences of metrics in the reviewed papers. This method requires input from the decision-maker and may have been influenced by subjective assessment. We addressed this limitation by repeating the evaluation and scoring of metrics by two experts during the iterative research process. This research focused on quantitative metrics that can be used for calculating team efficiency. In follow-up research, we may review the analyzed papers and metrics again from the perspective of team maturity and qualitative (soft) criteria. In addition, some metrics can be seen as logical parts of other metrics. We addressed this potential issue by carefully reviewing all identified metrics and repeating the review process to maintain the same level of granularity for all metrics in the metrics synthesis and results. Specific metrics could also be included in multiple domains or groups, thus forming an M:N relation instead of a 1:N relation. However, we identified only one such metric, which was *Team size*. In this case, we followed the paper by Almeida [3] and included *Team size* only in the Sprint domain. Finally, the final weights of the metrics do not follow the Pareto, or 80:20, rule [38]. The deviation from the Pareto principle indicates that Scrum efficiency depends on multiple factors rather than a few dominant ones, a conclusion we plan to explore further through direct field research.

6. Conclusions

In this research, we identified the key metrics that affect Scrum team efficiency through weighted prioritization: the five most important metrics are *Velocity*, *Cycle time*, *Work capacity*, *Focus factor*, and *Targeted value increase*, followed by additional metrics ranked by their weights. To address this research gap, we conducted a multi-criteria analysis combining semantic network construction, literature review, and the analytic network process. No prior research had applied quantitative decision theory using these methods to systematically assess Scrum team efficiency metrics. Our research identifies the key metrics needed to evaluate Scrum team efficiency. By identifying and ranking these metrics according to their calculated weights, organizations can now prioritize their improvement efforts strategically, directing resources toward the most impactful factors. Our results align with established research in agile project management and software development, validating the generalizability of our findings.

This paper represents the first phase of comprehensive research into Scrum team maturity. Future work will validate these findings through field studies in commercial organizations using agile methodologies, where practical constraints may reveal additional nuances or contextual factors. A custom software solution will operationalize these metrics, enabling organizations to evaluate team efficiency on a daily basis and support continuous maturity improvement. By translating these research insights into practical tools, Scrum teams can systematically assess their performance, allocate attention according to metric weights, and ultimately enhance their effectiveness in dynamic software development environments.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Josef Kunhart: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Jan Bartoška:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Supplementary materials are available at <https://zenodo.org/records/20367314> under a CC BY 4.0 license.

Appendix A. Metrics that affect Scrum team efficiency

Metric	Domain	Group	Weight
Velocity	Team	Performance	0.0971
Cycle time	Team	Performance	0.0706
Work capacity	Team	Performance	0.0530
Focus factor	Team	Motivation	0.0353
Targeted value increase	Team	Performance	0.0353
Estimation accuracy	Sprint	Review/Demo	0.0259
Sprint Burn-down	Artifacts	Sprint Backlog	0.0259
Defect count	Tech	Quality	0.0259
Defect count per User Story	Tech	Quality	0.0259
Test automation percentage	Tech	Testing	0.0207
Defect removal percentage	Tech	Quality	0.0207
Defects severity	Tech	Quality	0.0207
Source lines of code	Tech	Quality	0.0207
Team size	Sprint	Planning	0.0207
Number of accepted User Stories	Sprint	Review/Demo	0.0207
Number of rejected User Stories	Sprint	Review/Demo	0.0207
Team satisfaction score	Team	Motivation	0.0177
Team member turnover	Team	Performance	0.0177
Interruption time	Team	Performance	0.0177
Team efficiency	Team	Performance	0.0177
Number of User Stories in the Sprint	Artifacts	Sprint Backlog	0.0155
Sprint length	Sprint	Planning	0.0103
Team member engagement score	Sprint	Planning	0.0103
Expected number of iterations	Sprint	Planning	0.0103
Estimated project duration	Sprint	Planning	0.0103
Acceptance tests per User Story	Tech	Testing	0.0103
Functional tests per User Story	Tech	Testing	0.0103
Unit tests per User Story	Tech	Testing	0.0103

(table continues)

Metric	Domain	Group	Weight
Test feedback time	Tech	Testing	0.0103
Number of added User Stories	Artifacts	Product Backlog	0.0103
Number of deleted User Stories	Artifacts	Product Backlog	0.0103
Number of User Stories in Backlog	Artifacts	Product Backlog	0.0103
Business value	Artifacts	Product Backlog	0.0103
Number of tasks in the Sprint	Artifacts	Sprint Backlog	0.0103
Time spent to implement a task	Artifacts	Sprint Backlog	0.0103
Time the User Story is open	Artifacts	Sprint Backlog	0.0103
Number of tasks	Sprint	Daily Scrum	0.0103
Number of tasks in progress	Sprint	Daily Scrum	0.0103
Number of impediments	Sprint	Daily Scrum	0.0103
Estimated time for a task	Sprint	Daily Scrum	0.0103
Remaining time for a task	Sprint	Daily Scrum	0.0103
Workload distribution per team member	Sprint	Daily Scrum	0.0103
Number of completed tasks that day	Sprint	Daily Scrum	0.0103
Number of User Stories completed in a Sprint	Sprint	Retrospective	0.0103
Number of tasks completed in a Sprint	Sprint	Retrospective	0.0103
Defects density	Tech	Quality	0.0103
Customer defects density	Tech	Quality	0.0103
Percentage of accepted User Stories	Sprint	Review/Demo	0.0103
Number of User Stories by status	Sprint	Review/Demo	0.0103
Number of User Stories in initial release plan	Sprint	Release	0.0103
Number of User Stories in actual release plan	Sprint	Release	0.0103
Number of User Stories in final release plan	Sprint	Release	0.0103
Number of unsatisfactory User Stories	Team	Motivation	0.0088
Say:do ratio	Team	Motivation	0.0088
Code complexity	Tech	Implementation	0.0052
Nested block depth	Tech	Implementation	0.0052
Weighted units of code	Tech	Implementation	0.0052
Application performance	Tech	Implementation	0.0052
Defect detection percentage	Tech	Quality	0.0052
Average time to fix defect	Tech	Quality	0.0052
Test coverage	Tech	Testing	0.0052

Table A.7: Key metrics that affect Scrum team efficiency (source: own)

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